

Analysis of Inclusive Practices of Regular Schools for Promoting Inclusive Education

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Abstract

The term inclusive education entails an approach to imparting education to learners with special needs and including them in the formal education system with other children. In the inclusive method of education, learners with special needs spend their time with those children who do not need any special assistance. The present study was an analysis of the inclusive practices of regular schools for fostering inclusive education. The method adopted was descriptive- survey. The sample selected for the study was teachers, working in different regular Government Schools. The findings of the study reveal that regular schools promote inclusive education by providing essential facilities and adopting suitable inclusive classroom practices.

Key words: Inclusive Education, Regular Schools, Inclusive Practices, Heterogenous Grouping, Co-operative teaching, Collaborative-problem solving.

Introduction

Inclusive education is including children with disabilities in regular classrooms that have been designed for children without disabilities. It refers to an education system that accommodates all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions confronting the school system. Including children with diverse abilities and from diverse backgrounds have to be met by creating child centred pedagogy capable of successfully educating all children. It leads to the development of social skills and better social interactions because learners are exposed to real environment in which they have to interact with other learners each one having unique characteristics, interests, and abilities. The non-disabled peer adopts positive attitudes and actions towards learners with disabilities as a result of studying together in an inclusive classroom. As it is cleared by Article 2, **Salamanca Statement** "*Regular Schools with inclusive orientation are the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society and achieving education for all; moreover, they provide an effective education to the majority of children and improve the efficiency and ultimately the cost effectiveness of the entire educational system*". The inclusive

education demands reconstructed educational thinking and practice in regular schools for the benefit of all students.

Inclusive education is a process of extensive provision of equal access to high quality education of children with special educational needs through the organization of education in general educational institutions, using personalized teaching methods and taking consideration of the educational and cognitive activities of children. Education of persons with disabilities should form an integral part of national educational planning, curriculum development and school organization (Rule 6 of the UN Standard Rules for Persons with disabilities.)

Inclusion in education is based on the belief that every child can learn and realize their full potential if provided equal chance to take part in School, supported with resources essential to one's condition and taught in a manner appropriate to one's needs. A child must receive education in an environment that is least restraining and is most conducive to his/her needs. This means that general education is the placement of first choice for all wherein a child with disabilities is with her/his peers without disabilities to the maximum degree possible. Such an education is called Inclusive Education. Throughout the 19th century, children with special needs were

institutionalized, separated and carelessly discriminated. The term inclusive education seemed in the late 1980s as a substitute to special education, to give access to children with special needs coming from diverse background. The implementation of inclusive innovations should include the partnership of School and community, integration of information and communication technologies and creative teaching methods. The prerequisites for the effectiveness of inclusive education are the productivity and self-efficacy of teachers, communication competence of educators, a partnership approach to solving problems that arise in the learning process (Lancaster, 2014). Hence, it is essential to develop a system of education which is competent to cater all the needs, individualities and distinct dissimilarities of all children.

Need and Significance of the Study

Inclusive education system worth the unique contributions of students of all backgrounds bring to the classroom and allow diverse groups to grow side by side, to the benefit of all. Inclusion can be planned in several ways and on different levels, but in the end, the teacher has to deal with a greater diversity within his or her class and has to adjust or prepare the curriculum in such a way that the needs of all pupils, those with Special Educational Needs (SEN), gifted pupils and their peers, are sufficiently met. In short, managing diversity is the key issue in the inclusive class rooms so that children with disabilities should not experience repeated distress but improvement through school with a constant desire for recognition and peer approval (Carrington, 1999). To deal with this diversity in the class, teachers needs inclusive practices. A better understanding of inclusive practices is therefore essential for nurturing, motivating and including children with special educational needs.

Statement of the problem

Inclusive education is a process of increasing the participation of all students in School, including those with disabilities.

It is an integral part of the general education system. Inclusion has been used to refer to the settlement of students with disabilities in ordinary class rooms alongside their peers. The inclusive method of education discards the use of special educational institutions that segregate learners with disabilities from those without disabilities. Inclusive education is the most effective way to give special need children a fair chance to go to school, learn and develop the skills they need to flourish (Corbett, 1999). The classroom environment and classroom practices should be conducive for these children to get the maximum benefit of education. The present study analyses the inclusive practices of regular schools for fostering inclusive education. The study is hence entitled as ***“Analysis of Inclusive Practices of Regular Schools for Promoting Inclusive Education”***.

Objectives

1. To study the facilities provided for inclusive education in regular schools
2. To analyze the classroom practices in regular schools for promoting inclusive education.

Hypotheses

1. The regular schools provide suitable facilities for promoting inclusive education.
2. The classroom practices of the regular schools support inclusive education.

Methodology

Method

The investigator adopted descriptive-survey method for the study as it affords chances for determining the predominant conditions and it is essentially a technique of quantitative description of the characteristics selected for the study. Since the present study aims to analyze the inclusive practices of the regular schools, descriptive survey method was found suitable for the study.

Population

Population of the study involves teachers from different Regular Schools.

Sample

Sample selected for the study involves 80 teachers working in various regular Government Schools of

Thiruvananthapuram, Kollam and Kozhikode districts of Kerala.

Tool and Technique used for the Study

1. Questionnaire
2. Interview

The investigator developed a questionnaire consisting of closed and open-ended questions for the teachers to seek the views and preference of inclusive practices. The questionnaire consists of 20 questions related to inclusive practices in the classroom. The investigator conducted an interview with the head of the institutions for collecting details related to the facilities provided for pupils with special educational needs.

Procedure adopted for the study

The survey part of the study is online based. The questionnaire was administered to the sample through google form. To find the facilities provided for pupils with special educational needs, the investigator conducted an interview with the Head of the institutions of selected schools.

Analysis and Interpretation

Analysis of the data collected by Survey part of the study

The data collected were analyzed by using bi-modal approach. The closed ended questions were analyzed quantitatively by calculating the percentages. The qualitative analysis of the open-ended part of the questionnaire were used for collecting the views of the teachers associated with the inclusive classroom practices.

Table I

Inclusive classroom Practices in Regular Schools

Class room Practices	Number	Percentage
Heterogenous grouping	56	70
Co-operative Teaching	16	20
Collaborative Problem Solving	08	10

Figure I: Inclusive classroom Practices in Regular Schools

From Table 1, it is clear that 70% of the teachers preferred heterogenous grouping as adaptable class room practice for promoting inclusive education in regular schools whereas 20% of teachers selected co-operative teaching and remaining 10% chosen Collaborative problem solving as suitable classroom practice for inclusive education. Interpretation and explanation of the above-mentioned findings were given below.

Heterogenous Grouping

Planning of co-operative learning activities, lead to divide the classroom into separate groups. Students will have to work together to complete the task in the groups. Heterogenous grouping is effective for inclusive class rooms as it is with diversity of pupils in the class room. Heterogenous grouping is grouping of diverse students by putting them together in the same co-operative learning group. This mixed group

may compromise students of varying educational levels, interests, special needs etc. Students are of approximately the same age but function on different academic, social, and emotional levels. This method of heterogenous grouping allows students to learn from each other. The active interaction with diverse individuals while at the same time sharing their unique abilities and interests will lead the developments of specially needed students. The targeted goals, alternative routes for learning, flexible instruction and the abundance of heterogenous ways of grouping improve inclusive education.

Co-operative Teaching

Teachers need to cooperate with their colleagues within the school and professionals outside the school. The co-operative teaching is an educational approach in which general and special educators work in a coactive and coordinated fashion to jointly teach. It is appropriate and effective for inclusive classroom because of having academically and behaviorally heterogenous students in an educationally integrated setting. The co-operative teaching is effective for the cognitive and affective developments of students. The cooperative teaching is effective, only if the system is flexible and all should recognize the profit of learning and teaching together.

Collaborative Problem-Solving

Teachers want help in including pupils with social and behavioral problems, an organized way of approaching undesired behavior in the classroom is an effective tool for declining the intensity of disorders during teaching. As in the case of inclusive class rooms, dynamic class rules and a set of borders, approved with all students along with appropriate incentives will always be effective.

II. Details of the Interview with the Head of the Schools

In order to study the facilities provided for pupils with special educational needs in regular schools, an interview was conducted with the Head of the institutions. Following

are the facilities provided in the regular schools. Transport facilities to the student with disabilities.

The removal of architectural barriers from schools for promoting inclusive education.

The supply of books, uniforms and other materials to pupils with special educational needs attending the schools. The grant of scholarships to differently abled students. Suitable modification in the examination system for the benefit of blind students, hearing impaired and student with low vision.

Reconstructing of curriculum for the benefit of pupils with special educational needs.

Tenability of Hypotheses

The schools using inclusive education will intends to help everyone. Rejoicing diversity, assisting everyone and providing special support of those pupils with special educational needs are their ethics. The hypotheses proposed, **Hypothesis I** -The regular schools provide suitable facilities for promoting inclusive education and **Hypothesis II**- The class room practices of the regular schools support inclusive education, were hence accepted.

Major Findings

The regular schools provide suitable facilities for promoting inclusive education. The class room practices of the regular schools supports inclusive education. Majority (70%) of teachers preferred heterogenous grouping as suitable class room practice for promoting inclusive education in regular schools.

Suggestions

To implement inclusion at regular schools' practice, innovations should be introduced into personnel policy, teacher training, professional development, competence development, in particular the ability to conjoin the educational needs of students. Teachers should accept and appreciate the new educational paradigm, new ways of unifying the educational process, development of educational and methodological provisions, mastering of modern methods and techniques to differentiate personality adapted teaching responsible to the individual needs of the

student. A positive constructivist approach of teachers promotes the effective implementation of inclusive innovations. The positive attitude and insight of inclusion by teachers should be based on the intensity of disability and the educational environment of the learner.

Conclusion

Regular schools must enable children to recognize, comprehend and appreciate other

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cultures and the needs of different people. The schools should sensitize all children towards understanding and accepting their differently abled counterparts. Education must inculcate the feeling of mutual appreciation and respect for one another. Thus, it can be concluded that schools using inclusive method of education will talk about helping everyone.